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**THE POETICS OF POST-9/11 AMERICAN STRUCTURAL
ISLAMOPHOBIA AND ARAB IDENTITY: YUSSEF EL GUINDI'S
BACK OF THE THROAT**

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Abstract

This study probes the problematics of post-9/11 American structural Islamophobia and Arab identity through Yussef El Guindi's play, Back of the Throat. American Arab represents the pathological condition of the Foucauldian lepor in the post-9/11 American panopticon. Arab/Muslim identity is criminalized and securitized by the FBI agents representing American Islamophobic state structure in the play. Furthermore, American Arabs are victims of cultural racism and Islamophobia in the post-9/11 surveillance state of America in El Guindi's Back of the Throat. The tropes of European Orientalism and American orientalism are deployed by the FBI agents in the delineation of Arabs. Arabs are projected as the new villains of modern history. El Guindi projects this bigotry of the American hegemon through his play, Back of the Throat. This study uses Khaled A. Beydoun's theoretical model of American Islamophobia for the analysis of the play. Beydoun's model of American Islamophobia is supplemented by Michael Foucault's panopticism. Further, Beydoun's model of American Islamophobia is supported by other theorists of Islamophobia. Edward W. Said's model of identity is utilized for probing for the identity of American Arabs. In addition, the study uses an interpretivist and historicist approach for the analysis of the relationship between American structural Islamophobia and Arab identity in the play.

Keywords: Islamophobia, Orientalism, panopticism, surveillance, filiation and affiliation

Introduction

Muslims were part of the American landscape before the birth of the American Republic. Jonathan Curiel (2015) writes that "the story of Islam in America really begins in the South, with the slave trade" (p.xxii). Thousands of Muslims landed on the states forming the present day United States as part of the historical slave trade. Curiel writes that "these Southern slaves formed the roots of American Islam, the roots of America itself" (p.xxii). Similarly, Timothy Marr (2006) writes that "Islam has figured in the fashioning of North American cultural definitions since as far back as the first years of European settlement" (p.2). Likewise, the Arabs had been part of the American historical imagination. The statue of "a robed and bearded Muhammad with a curved sword in one hand and the Quran in the other" in the Supreme Court of the United States reflects American perceptions of Islam and Arabs (p.1). Michael W. Suleiman (1999) charts out the "two major waves of Arab immigration to North America" (p.1). The first wave of Arab immigration started from 1870s and lasted till the Second World War. The second wave lasted from World War II till the present times. The first waves of Arab immigrants mostly hailed from the region of Greater Syria and were predominantly Christians. The second wave included Arabs from all regions, religions and sects. Further they were delineated through regional and racial terminology in American imagination. Arabs imaginary of themselves in America is grown from "sojourners" to settlers and settlement after World Wars (p.4). The children of the earlier generations of American Arabs integrated to American culture and life. Suleiman writes that Americanization and assimilationist approach demanded "shedding old loyalties, the traditional culture, and the Arabic language" (p.9). Despite the immersion of Arabs in American culture, mostly American Arabs suffered a "politics of exclusion" and "political racism" in American polity (p.13).

The roots of American Islamophobia lie in the genesis of America. The accidental discovery of the New World by Christopher Columbus was itself premised on anti-Muslim sentiments. Ziauddin Sardar (2002) highlights 'the anti-Muslim rage' in the very birth of America. He writes that the historical odyssey of Columbus was motivated by anti-Muslim sentiments after the fall of Granada (1492) as Ferdinand and Isabella "gave their approval for his novel proposal to continue the crusade against the infidel, seeking the East by sailing westward across the Atlantic" (p.149). Furthermore, the specter of Islam loomed large in American imagination after the American Revolution. In the constitutional debates of 1787-8, the Ottoman

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despotism was projected the contrative image of the American identity. American perceptions towards Islam were further molded by American encounter with Barbary Pirates. The Barbary Wars were fought under the leadership of Thomas Jefferson and its heroes were equated with the Founding Fathers in American imagination. Robert J. Allison (1995) writes that “the Revolutionaries had beaten the British; this generation had bested the scourge of Christendom” (p.204). The Muslims of Barbary Coast of North Africa and their stories of piracy led the American imagination to describe them “Monsters of Africa” and “powers of Darkness” (p.140). These notions about Muslims and Arabs had penetrated the official machinery and psychology of the United States. The spectacular 9/11 unleashed the floodgates of the deep-rooted American structural Islamophobia and Arabophobia. Keeping this journey of American Arabs and Muslims in the background, this article probes the dynamics of American structural Islamophobia and Arab identity in Yussef El Guindi’s play *Back of the Throat*.

Research Question: How Yussef El Guindi’s *Back of the Throat* projects the poetics of Post-9/11 American Islamophobia and Arab identity?

Theoretical Framework: This study utilizes Khaled A. Beydoun’s model of American Islamophobia for probing the condition of American Arabs in El Guindi’s play. Beydoun’s model is complemented by Michael Foucault’s panopticism and Edward Said’s concept of identity. Beydoun (2023) writes that “Islamophobia is the strategic framing of Muslim identities and behavior as presumptive evidence of terrorism” (p.219). He explains American Islamophobia through its historical roots as; “It is a system that redeploys stereotypes of Muslims deeply rooted in the collective American imagination and endorsed by formative case law, foundational policy on immigration and citizenship, and the writings and rhetoric of this nation’s founding fathers” (p.18). Further, linking American Islamophobia to European Orientalist tradition, Beydoun writes, that “Orientalism is the mother of Islamophobia” (p.75). Nathan Lean (2012) writes that Islamophobia is “the fear of Islam and Muslims. It is the fear that then leads to hatred, hostility and discrimination” (p.18).

Research Methodology

This study is interpretivist in its nature. The study utilizes close reading as tool for the textual analysis of the primary text. Yussef El Guindi’s play *Back of the Throat* (2006), published in Allan Havis’ *American Political Plays after 9/11*, is used as the primary text for probing the problematics of Arab identity and American structural Islamophobia. In addition, critical works on El Guindi’s plays and scholarship on the relationship of Arabs/Muslims and America are the secondary sources utilized for this study. The study uses textual and contextual (historicist) approach for the analysis of the relationship between American structural Islamophobia and Arab identity in El Guindi’s play, *Back of the Throat*.

Analysis

The spectacular 9/11 attack on the American symbols of economic and military power and the consequent War on Terror made Muslims targets of American rage. American Arabs and Muslims became victims of the War on Terror on American domestic as well as international stage. Domestically, American Muslims, South Asians and Middle Eastern Arabs became suspect and targets of the Homeland Security Act. As the perpetrators of 9/11 hailed from Arab countries, American Arabs were criminalized by their associative guilt. Arab identity was equated with terrorist identity. Consequently, Muslim suffered collective punishment for the attacks on the World Trade Centre and Pentagon. Literary writers, novelists and playwrights, responded through fiction and theatre to the rampant Islamophobia and War on Terror narrative. Mohsin Hamid, H. M. Naqvi and Laila Hallaby challenged the War on Terror narrative through fiction. Similarly, Yussef El Guindi projected American Islamophobia through his play, *Back of the Throat*.

El Guindi represents the Arab voice against American state terrorism through his plays. He stands against American Arabophobia and Islamophobia in the post-9/11 scenario. Michael Malek Najjar (2019) writes that El Guindi represents the survival of an Arab/Muslim immigrant in the context of rampant xenophobia, Arabophobia and Islamophobia in post-9/11 America (p.xvi). El Guindi tells about his Arab identity as “I am also creating plays from a hyper-aware immigrant perspective, and doing it from a uniquely Arab and Muslim perspective” (p.xviii). El Guindi (2008) tells that “*Back of the Throat* began as a paranoid thought game” in the aftermath of Bush Patriot Act and American paranoid state aroused by the fear of an amorphous enemy (p.2). Najjar writes that El Guindi was a great admirer of the English playwright George Bernard Shaw and gave all his characters “strong arguments that justified their actions” (p. xx). He further writes that El Guindi’s play, *Back of the Throat* “subverts the hegemonic narrative that states, “you are either

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with us or with the terrorists” (p.xx). Najjar (2014) considers El Guindi to be the most provocative voice of Arab American drama representing “cultural nationalism and a form of resistance literature” (p. 4).

El Guindi (2006) projects the dialectics of American Arab/Muslim identity in post-/11 America through *Back of the Throats*. Khalid, the protagonist of the play, is caught in a web of identities ranging from biology to association. Arab identity has linguistic, cultural, racial and religious connotations. Further, Arab identity has been fluid and has anti-colonial and nationalist dimension in the past. Historically, the important component of Arab identity is Islam. Edward W. Said (1983) sees human identity in terms of filiation and affiliation. He writes that “the filiative scheme belongs to the realms of nature and of “life,” where as affiliation belongs to culture and society” (p.20). Khalid is the representative of the Arab American community as well as common Arab identity of the Arab nations. Furthermore, he stands for the broader American Muslim category as well as the universal category of Muslim identity in the play. Bartlet tells Khalid “you’re a Muslim and an Arab” suggests these layers of Khalid’s identity (p.151). Further, his Muslim identity is evident from the presence of the Holy Quran and Islamic calligraphy in his room. Khalid projects himself as a cultural Muslim demonstrated by his remarks “I am not religious myself” (p.138). In addition to his Arab/ Muslim identity, like El Guindi himself, Khalid is affiliated to America. His American identity is visible from his American citizenship. Khalid claims his American identity by telling Bartlet “did I mention I’m a citizen” (p.140). Khalid’s identity is the product of Middle Eastern roots and American routes. Khalid complicates the identity of host/home country, insider/outsider and internal/external Other of American Arabs. The intersectional state of American Arab identity and collective Arab identity is symptomatic of a pathological condition in the post-9/11 American Islamophobic imagination projected by El Guindi’s *Back of the Throat*.

El Guindi projects the United States like Bentham’s Panopticon for the American Arab community in his play, *Back of the Throat*. Just as *1984* represents Orwellian totalitarian state, in similar way, *Back of the Throat* projects the post-Orwellian Surveillance of the United States in the context of post-9/11. El Guindi projects the American State surveillance premised on American structural Islamophobia. The state surveillance, detention without a cause and International black sites or war prisons for Muslims demonstrate how US works as a panopticon state. Written in the context of the PATRIOT Act (2001), Operation TIPS (2002) and Special Registration (2002) and Homeland Security, El Guindi’s *Back of the Throat* projects US panopticism. Michael Foucault (1977) writes that the panopticon “is a segmented, immobile, frozen space” for the pathological community (p.201).

El Guindi projects Arab as a leper, the pathological one, for the United States in the Post-9/11 world. Khalid, the protagonist in El Guindi’s play *Back of the Throat*, represents the Arab pathology of associative guilt and contagion of the 9/11 terrorists and needs to be quarantined. Foucault writes that “the surveillance is based on a system of permanent registration” in the panopticon (p.202). The racial profiling, registration and bio-genetic impressions of the Arabs and Muslims in the Post-9/11 America testifies that Arabs represented a pathological condition for the US. Consequently the Arab collectivity and community suffered from the “internment of the psyche” as Nadine Naber calls this condition (p.40). “A compact model of the disciplinary mechanism” worked for the surveillance and management of Arab community in the post-9/11 world. Bartlet and Carl, the FBI agents are the representative of the US disciplinary mechanism in El Guindi’s play, *Back of the Throat*.

Khalid, a representative of the American Arab community, is the focus of “axial visibility” (p.206). Schiavini (2021) writes that visibility for American Arabs implies Arabophobia. Bartlet projects the visibility of Khalid - by extension Arab American-community – from his relational and spatial position. Bartlet highlights the associative and relational visibility as Khalid’s “background happens to be the place where most of this crap is coming from. *So naturally the focus is going to be on you*” (p.151). American Arabs and Arabs in general became the focus of Academy, politics, media and cultural industry in the post-9/11 context. Hind Naji Hussein Ithawi (2018, p.23) writes that “9/11 has exposed Arab-Americans to negative visibility”. Bartlet dissociates his ethnicity from Khalid’s identity. In the Panopticon, the pathological one “is the object of information, never a subject in communication” (p. 206). This is evident from Bartlet telling Khalid “that anything you say here will be in strict confidence” (p.141). The FBI agents tell Khalid that they want to “create an atmosphere where you might feel more willing to offer up information” (p. 150). Instead of true Arab voice, the American Arab community is forced to play ‘good Muslim’ for the imperial American policy. This condition of the Arab American community is visible from Khalid “not being able to address whatever

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accusations have been made against me. It is like battling ghosts” (p.141). Khalid’s subjectivity is erased by Khalid’s associative guilt of being Arab and the circumstantial deductions made by the FBI agents from his books and porn magazine in his apartment. Khalid is reduced to a frozen state in terms of physical and psychological conditions. This erasing of Arab self/subjectivity and citizenship highlights the power of the US panopticon state.

Foucault writes that “the panopticon functions as a kind of laboratory of Power” based on “power relations” (p.210). El Guindi projects the dynamics of American power in his play, *Back of the Throat* as “the United States of America is the biggest, strongest eight-hundred pound gorilla on the block” (p.166). This image highlights the role of US as world bully violating international norms for pursuing its global imperialism. Similarly, Ivan Lacko (2015) that “*Back of the Throat* draws on the power relations and social structures known in totalitarian societies” (p.257). Lacko connects El Guindi with the fictional worlds of Orwell, Kafka and Pinter and links his work with their projection of Western totalitarian experiences and their co-mingling of facts and myths. El Guindi highlights the totalitarian panopticism of America in the post-9/11 through the image of “eight-hundred pound gorilla” in the play. El Guindi highlights the power of the disciplinary mechanism of the US surveillance machinery through FBI officials, Carl and Bartlet. When Khalid is not yielding the desired results for the FBI agents, Carl suggests “to bring the full weight of our authority” on him (p.170). The power relations of the FBI agents vs. Khalid (the United States and the Arab American community) is visible from Bartlet telling Khalid “I’m government official, uninvited, and you have been yanked out of your routine” (p.142). El Guindi counters this hegemonic imperialism through his play, *Back Of the Throat*.

This totalitarian surveillance and disciplinary mechanism brings the American structural Islamophobia into full light. Beydoun (2018) defines structural Islamophobia as the pervasive fear and suspicion among governmental institutions and its representatives about Muslims and Islam. Structural Islamophobia is built through laws and policies on the presumed threat of Muslim identity to the national security of America. Beydoun writes that American structural Islamophobia is based on neo-orientalist tropes embedded in the structure of governmental institutions, legislature, executive and Judiciary. The PATRIOT Act, the first and second Muslim Bans and Counter Radicalization programs are the examples of the American structural Islamophobia. Nathan Lean (2019) terms it “a hegemonic political structure” pursuing the project of restructuring the world culturally and economically and creating an atmosphere for the manifestation of Islamophobia (p.30). Naber describes Islamophobia “as a form of imperial racism” (p.135). Islamophobia, a complex of different variables, operates in American official machinery as evident from El Guindi’s *Back of the Throat*.

Yussef El Guindi highlights American structural Arabophobia and Islamophobia through the FBI agents in his play, *Back of the Throat*. The two FBI agents, Bartlet and Carl, are the representative of the totalitarian American government. The protagonist of the play, Khalid, is the victim of American structural Islamophobia. Bartlet tells Khalid “you are a Muslim and an Arab. Those are the bad asses currently making life a living hell” (p.151). This statement suggests the condition of Muslims and Arabs in America as religiously and racially suspect. Arab identity, the product of Bedouin culture and Islam, is associated with terrorism in the post-9/11 American imagination. Raphael Patai (1973) connects Arab identity with Bedouin culture. He writes that “the conceptual association between Arab and Bedouin was and remained so close that frequently when an Arab author uses “Arab” what he actually means is “Bedouin” (p.12). Patai’s book *the Arab Mind* was considered the bible of the neo-cons of Bush administration towards Arabs. The neo-cons attitude towards Arabs and the treatment met to the prisoners at Guantanamo by the hands of American administration was the outcome of Patai’s book According to Patai, Islam was superimposed on the Bedouin substratum of the Arab mind. Consequently, Arab identity is synonymous with terrorist identity. Sahar Aziz (2022) writes that Islamophobia and its associative anti-Muslim racism criminalizes and securitizes Muslims as threat to the existence and sovereignty of the nation. Aziz writes that Christian theology is the philosophical foundation of the racialization of blacks and Muslims in America. The statement of FBI agents reflects the post-9/11 discourse of “the racialization and criminalization of Arabs and Islam” by the Bush Administration as Evelyn Alsultany (2012, p.53) writes. Furthermore, this statement represents Muslims and Arabs as monolith and equates extreme and mainstream as Pratt (2019) suggests.

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The story of American Arabs/Muslims negates reductionist and monolithic approach. American Arabs hail from different religions and regions. Further, their emigration to America was motivated by various factors. The motivation of American Arabs for emigration included an escape from Ottoman despotism, avoiding Ottoman military service during the First World War, the pursuit of economic well-being and American dream. Similarly, Muslims from various regions and ethnicities are forming the category of American Muslims. Analyzed in American domestic context, Bartlet's projection of American Arabs and Muslims displays a reductionist and monolithic approach.

Moreover, Bartlet's statement stems from the collective memory of the US. Salaita (2007) writes that Arabs were framed "an ethnic icon" in the nineteenth century and came to the full light of political eminence in post-9/11 America. Salaita views American anti-Arab racism vitally connected with geopolitics. Highlighting the pervasive stereotypes of the Arabs, Jack G. Shaheen (2009) writes that Arabs are projected as the cultural "other" of America by Hollywood films. Arabs as racial and religious 'Other' is threatening Western civilization and its Judeo-Christian heritage. This image of Arab resisting the American geo-political interests was augmented by Jamal Abdul Nasir's Arab nationalism and his nationalization of the Suez Canal and the Oil Embargo of the OPEC in 1973 Arab-Israeli War. After the Iranian revolution in 1979, the threat from the Middle East became ideological culminating in the tragedy of 9/11. All the hijackers of 9/11 were Arab Muslims blending Arab nationalism and radical Islam. Because of these developments, there grew a nexus of Islamophobia and Arabophobia in America reflected by the statement of the FBI agent. Najib (2022) views Islamophobia as a "systemic anti-Muslim racism that targets expressions of Muslimness" (p.35). Racism is part of the American collective psyche. Erik Love (2017) writes that Islamophobia as a form of racism is permeated into the fabric of American institutional machinery. Eric Love writes that Islamophobia and white supremacy originates from the same base and are built into the habitat of American institutions. Eric Love highlights the problematic of Islamophobia and racism through the example of Balbir Singh Sodhi and Cameron Mohammad. This frame of "looks Muslim" makes Arab Christians and South Asian Hindus and Sikhs vulnerable to Islamophobic assaults.

El Guindi highlights the "Green Peril" of the Culture Talk through his play. Bartlet highlights the gravitational pull of the American foreign policy and its associative aggression towards by Muslims telling Khalid "Yesterday the Irish and the Poles, today it is you" (p.151). American Arabs became the victim of post-9/11 American McCarthyism. Just as Japanese during the Second World War and Communists after the War were hunted down, similarly, Arabs/Muslims became the target of the American ghost hunt. Mamdani (2003) writes that "Green Peril" haunted Culture Talk and American imagination in the Post-Cold War era (p.15). The culture Talk projected 'Radical Islam' as the new threat to American geopolitical and strategic interests after the fall of communism. Muslims and Arabs are perceived as the villains of post-9/11 world history. The American war on Muslims disguised as 'War on Terror' clearly reflects American foreign policy in the post-9/11 world. Esposito (2019) in his Foreword to Peter Morey's *Contesting Islamophobia* writes that contemporary Islamophobia is triggered by the political events of the last decades in the Muslim world. Furthermore, he writes that the collapse of Soviet union implied that "Radical Islamic Fundamentalism" would be the global antagonist to American imperialist agenda (p. xv).

Yussef El Guindi projects American cultural racism towards American Arabs through the FBI agents' attitude to Arabic language. In the opening of the play, Bartlet displays derision towards Arabic language through his efforts to pronounce Khalid's name. He tries to pronounce Khalid as "Kaled" and "Halid" (p. 139). This kind of distortion and mimicry was also played with the name of Zohran Mamadani by his opponents during election for New York Mayorship. However, Bartlet ends this mimical theatrics by saying "it is the back of the throat thing" (p.139). The title of the play, *Back of the Throat*, is based on this statement. The title of the play and Bartlet's relinquishing his efforts to correctly pronounce "Khalid" becomes symbolic of Arab's condition in America. American structural Islamophobia can't allow Arab Americans to become part of its body fabric. Further, Arabs are stuck in American throat in the post 9/11 world. The presumed racial, religious and cultural inferiority of Muslim societies are highlighted by the behaviors of the FBI agents. American structural racism becomes visible from Bartlet telling Khalid "you come here with shit, from shit countries" (p.154). Bartlet's comments smear the collective identity and history of Arabs. The erasure of Arab's contribution to sciences and human civilization reflects American imperialist propaganda. Ibrahim Kalin (2011) connects racism and Islamophobia. He writes that the old racism premised on biological inferiority re-

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emerges as cultural, ethnic and religious racism in modern parlance. Similarly Meer and Noorani (2008) presents the definitions of cultural racism as “new racism”, “Neo-racism”, “differentialist racism” by Balcer Balibar and Modood (p.197). They write that Cultural racism and differences are based on the logic of nature in Western imaginary. Cultural racism is the outcome of the inferiorization and essentialization of other cultures.

El Guindi projects American structural Islamophobia and cultural racism responsible for the suspension of the civil liberties and citizenship of Muslim immigrants. When Khalid speaks of his rights and citizenship in the play, Bartlet tells him “*I will fucking vomit*” by hearing an immigrant speaking of his rights (p.153). Bartlet’s vomiting is suggestive of the lava of American cultural racism deployed against Arabs in the play. This miniature image is enlarged by President Trump’s Executive Orders popularly known as “Muslim Ban”. Citizenship is connected to Western tradition opposed to authoritarian Muslim history and culture in American imagination. Consequently, American Arabs connected to Authoritarian Arab tradition are not entitled to American and Western values. One strand of Islamophobic thoughts is that American Muslims are not really Americans and consequently have no rights. Although Arabs have passed the “whiteness” test but still they occupy the lowest position in American racial spectrum. Suleiman writes that Arabs are seen “honorary whites” in American imagination. American Arabs’ loyalties are suspected in the post-9/11 world. Khalid reminds Bartlet of the American constitution as “this is still America, and I will not be treated this way” (p.153). Bartlet is not prepared to listen to Khalid’s “this is still America” narrative and warns of severe treatment. (p.153). Khalid and Bartlet represent the two contrastive visions of America; the pluralist and the nativist. Khalid’s insistence on citizenship and identification with the multiculturalist and pluralist vision is rebutted by Bartlet. Bartlet presents an exclusivist and exclusionary vision of America by not listening to immigrants’ narrative of their rights enunciated by the founding fathers in American constitution.

The question of Muslim citizenship had deep roots in American constitutional history. The citizenship of Muslims had been a focal point of controversy in the constitutional debate of 1787-8. The founding fathers like Washington, Jefferson and James Madison pursuing a pluralistic vision of America were in favor of Muslim inclusivity in the body politics of the United States. However, majority of the American Protestants were holding views, about Islam inherited from their European intellectual heritage. Martin Luther, John Calvin and Fox were the formative influences building American protestant perspective of Islam. In addition to American protestant vision of Islam, Spellberg (2013) writes, prejudice towards Muslims existed among Catholics on American continent. Spellberg writes that during the time of American Revolution, theological and political polemics against Islam existed in Europe and America. The post-9/11 America context resurrects these old prejudices towards Muslims and Arabs’ citizenship rights in America.

In the Post-9/11 scenario, critics of American foreign policy were suspected and associated with terrorism. They were considered sympathizers to the cause of the perpetrators of 9/11. Just as AC in H.M.Naqvi’s Home Boy is kept in Detention Centre for critiquing Bush Foreign policy on terrorism charges, similar suspicion of anti-Americanism is felt towards Khalid in *Back of the Throat*. Khalid tells Beth “I am just saying we have to look for the “why” (p.165). Holding American imperialism and policies responsible for 9/11 is considered justification and sympathy for the perpetrators. America, addicted to a triumphalist and exceptionalist image of herself, is not prepared for guilt-consciousness. This is evident when Beth tells Khalid why should we “paralyze ourselves by examining our conscience” (p.166). America, in pursuit of global capitalism and global imperialism, is not ready to revisit its policies but puts the blame squarely on Muslims being envious of American civilization. This is how Beth vents American thinking in response to Khalid’s quest for the “why” of 9/11. Beth tells Khalid that pursuing the question of “why” means that there is “a legitimate reason” for the action of terrorists (p.166). America caught in imperial hubris and siege mentality is not prepared to see its own image but pursued the ghost hunting War on Terror. The U.S is not prepared to accept the guilt of its foreign policy in the Muslim and Arab world. Bartlet like DeLillo’s *Falling Man* exonerates the U.S imperialism from the predicament of the Arab world and associates Muslim anger in terms of “how overrun you are by us” (p.172). Maha Hilal (2021) writes that the “narrative of US victimhood” is used a moral justification for War on Terror and its associative American aggression (p.9). There is complete dissociation of American imperialism and the event of 9/11 in American thoughts. In the context of 9/11, ‘Good Muslims’ and ‘Good Arabs’ were expected to cooperate with U.S through different roles. Good Muslims/Arabs were expected to raise their voice against radical Islam, play as provocateurs in FBI’s sting

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operations. This is what the FBI officials expect from Khalid. Bartlet presses Khalid “to cooperate” with FBI agents.

American Islamophobia projects Islam as a radical ideology and Muslims as radicals and terrorists. Nathan Lean writes that after the Iranian Revolution Radical Islam and Islamic terrorism was perceived as “the next imminent ideological threat to the West” (p.34). The seismic catastrophe of 9/11 brought American in confrontation with radical Islam. President Bush used the term “Islamofacism” for the projection of Islam as a radical ideology. Lean writes that American foreign policy and its assocaitive rhetoric couched the War on Terror in religious idioms and language. Terms like “Islamic Fascism”, “Islamic terrorism” and “Political Islam” were used by the so called experts and commenators on Islam. This religious-cum-ideological idiom of the War on Terror became visible from President Bush using the term “Crusade” for it.

El Guindi highlights this American imaginary of Islam and its association with radical ideologies through his play, *Back of the Throat*. Bartlet describes Khalid “a left-leaning subversive with Maoist tendencies” due to the presence of books on various topics in Khalid’s apartment (p.148). Khalid, being a writer, have books on guns, assassins, “Quotations from Chairman MaoTsetung” “Militant Islam”, “Covering Islam”, “A Manual of the Oppressed”, “Theatre of the Oppressed” and books on different subjects in his apartment. Bartlet projects Khalid having “plans for tunneling under the White House” (p.147). This is reminiscent of McCarthyism when communists and Soviets were percieved threat to the national security of America.

El Guindi projects the Orientalist notions of perverted sexuality of the Arabs through his play, *Back of the Throat*. The FBI officer, Bartlet, finding a porn magazine in Khalid’s apartment speaks of him as “unnormal individual” (p.147). The context for his ‘abnormality’ is the Porn magazine found in his room by the FBI agents. Khalid projects his interests in sex from the American perspective – “the place of erotica in society” (p. 143). Barlet sees Khalid from the Orientalist perspective of pedophilia – “weird fantasies” and “child porn” – associated with Arabs and Muslims. (p.148). Perverted sexuality associated with Arab psyche is visible from Bartlet’s projection of Khalid “perverted little fantasies” (p.154). Joseph A. Massad (2007) writes that Western Orientalists and Western anthropologist were interested in the sexual practics of the Arabs. They produced an account of “ethnopornography”of the Arabs highlighting their moral decadence for imperial/colonial designs (p.8). The Orientalists considered the sexuality of Arabs of “a different qualitative and quantitative order” (p.15). There seems a resonance of Negro’s sexuality in the projection of Arab libido. Edward Said highlights the Orientalists’ projection of the Arab as “an oversexed degenerate” in American films and dramas (p.287). Just as the Ottoman sultan was represented as neurotic sexual being on the early modern English stage through “Turk plays”, similarly Arabs are represented with perverted sexuality in the American Imagination.

El Guindi projects the American Orientalist image of the “the smiling little Semite” for Arabs in *Back of the Throat*. Semitism and Aryanism were European constructs for establishing European superemacy. Arabs and Jews were Semites in European imaginary. However, Arabs and Jews had journeyed in opposite direction. Jews had become Westernized and assimilated into Western civilization through the matrix of ‘Judeo-Christain heritage’. Jews conversion to Christianity in Europe speaks of the assimilation of Jews to Western civilization whose underbelly is Christian heritage. On the other hand, Arabs had become oriental and Semites. Consequently, Arabs had become metaphor of cunningness and deciet in the Orientalists’imagination and culturalists. Arabs are the smiling villains in post-9/11 American imagination. Arabs are projected deceptive and cunning in American imaginary. Edward Said writes that “the transference of a popular anti-Semitic animus from a Jewish to an Arab target was made smoothly” in the context of Oil embargo of 1973. Arabs are portrayed treacherous and intriguers by the popular American culture. The factor for the cunning nature of the Arabs is Arab culture for the neo-orientalists and Culture Talk intellectuals.

American structural Islamophobia is premised on the Orientalist epistemology. Beydoun writes that “Islamophobia is the modern progeny of Orientalism” (p.36).Similarly, Fuad Shaban (1991) writes that American Orientalism is the product of European orientatlsim and America’s own engagement with Muslim world. Shaban terms it “a national cultural dialogue” (p.vii). Douglas Little (2008) writes that American Orientatlsim is premised on Social Darwinism entailing “the racial inferiority” of Muslims and belief on the superiority of America (p.17). The pervasive influence of Orientalist tropes about Muslims in general and Arabs in particular are visible in the resurgence of contemporary Islamophobia. Edward Said (1978) writes

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Orientalism is successfully adapted to the new imperialism of America for dominating Asia. Consequently, the Arab world is the satellite of America politically, culturally and intellectually. Al-Sultany (2012) writes about the Orientalist projection of Arabs in the popular culture of America as “as rich oil sheikhs, sultry belly dancers, harem girls, veiled oppressed women and, most notably, terrorists” (p. 07). This projection of Arabs is articulated through the three Bs (billionaires, belly dancers and bombers).

El Guinda projects the American Orientalist discourse about Islam and Arabs through the image of the “fucking burqa” in his play, *Back of the Throat*. The Orientalist-racist image of “fucking burqa” is projected by Beth while discussing 9/11 as a rape of America. The veil associated with Muslim and Arab women have a long orientalist-colonialist and imperialist history. Burqa is the symbol of the medievalist and traditionalist thinking of Muslim societies in American thinking. The question of veiling Muslim woman (burqa, scarf etc.) has been the bone of contention between Muslim fundamentalists, nationalists, feminists and imperialists. The Muslim fundamentalists consider veil as a religious marker and symbol of religiosity. The cultural nationalists view the veil as symbol of cultural identity. On the other hand, feminists and imperialists consider the veiling of Muslim woman as symbolic of patriarchy and repression. Nadine Naber writes that American narrative on Muslim veiling criticizes Muslim women for their veiling and projects them as extensions of the Muslim misogynist men. Naber further writes that American Neo-orientalist discussions on Muslim veiling represent Muslim women through the binary of “with us” or with “violent Muslim others” (p.138). Highlighting the historical account of the American narrative of Muslim women, Lean writes, that the stories forged by the US soldiers and naval commanders during the Barbary Wars about “Islamic gender relations” still dominate American landscape (p.94). Keeping Naber and Lean’s analyses of the Veil of Muslim woman, Beth’s comments highlight the deep-rooted orientalism of the Collective Unconscious of America.

The image of “fucking burqa” provides the historical justification for America’s imperial War on Terror in the post-9/11 context. The point of Beth’s reference to ‘the fucking burqa’ is to implicate Khalid in a misogynist Arab culture. Furthermore, the figure of the burqa-clad woman of the Muslim world, a symbol of the oppressed Muslim woman, is connected with imperialist wars and western Orientalist-feminist politics and ideologies. This is why American imperial wars in Afghanistan and Iraq were justified by the most conservative president of the United States as wars of liberation. Furthermore, his wife, Laura Bush, emerged as the champion for the rights of Afghan women. This construction of ‘the oppressed Muslim woman’ has long historical roots in American imagination. The First American encounter, the Barbary Wars, was also called war of liberation for the cause of Muslim Woman. Lean writes that brainwashed by their patriarchs and internalized the patriarchal structure and misogynist traditions of the Muslim societies, the Muslim women need saving from themselves in American discourse of Muslim woman and veiling.

El Guindi projects the contribution/burden typology of American Arabs through his play. Khalid tells Bartlet “I am making a contribution” (p.155). Khalid contributes to American academy and cultural industry through his art of story writing. He has received grants and prize for his past stories from American academy. Historically, America was made great by immigrants by their creativity and enterprise. However, the influx of large scale Muslim immigrants in the last decades of the twentieth century alarmed the white nationalists and environmentalist activists. Tom Gjelton (2015) writes that “the story of subversive Muslims in America beautifully reinforced their nativist inclinations” (p.285). Gjelton writes that 9/11 presented Muslims “the biggest challenge to America’s welcoming attitude since the 1920’s and a fundamental test of the 1965 promise of a bias-free immigration policy” (p.285). This anti-Arab/Muslim immigration attitude is visible from the FBI agents towards Khalid. Bartlet negates Khalid’s contribution to America as a writer. He tells Khalid you are draining from America. Bartlet implies that American Arabs “pick all the good things this country has to offer and give nothing back and then dump on us” (p.155). The anti-immigrant approach towards Muslim is visible in the policies of current Trump administration.

Like Tariq Ali, Yusef El Guindi rebuts the image of Khalid as terrorist through his projection as a writer. Khalid, the protagonist of the play like Idrisi in Tariq Ali’s *A Sultan in Palermo* is a Socratic hero. Although a shadow of the Muslim polymath, Idrisi, Khalid pursues intellectual dreams. Reading and writing are his dominions. Like Idrisi who was well-versed in the ancients, Khalid is a voracious reader. Being a writer, he reads books on every subject. He tells Bartlet “I am a writer” (p.144). Khalid tells Bartlet “that is my big thing, reading” (p.140). The projection of Khalid as a writer is to rebut the terrorist identity associated with Arabs in the post-9/11 scenario. Just as historically Arabs contributed to the Western civilization in sciences

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and philosophy, likewise Khalid contributes to American Academy. Just as Idrisi preserves life through his map-making, similarly, Khalid preserves the experiences of human life through his art of story writing.

References

- Allison, R. J. (1995). *The Crescent Obscured: The United States and the Muslim World 1776-181*. Chicago: the University of Chicago Press
- Alsultany, E. (2012). *Arabs and Muslims in the Media: Race and Representation after 9/11*. New York: New York University Press.
- Aziz, S. F. (2022). *The Racial Muslim: When Racism Quashes Religious Freedom*. California: University of California Press.
- Beydoun, K. A. (2018). *American Islamophobia; Understanding the Roots and Rise of Fear*. California: University of California Press.
- Beydoun, K. A. (2023). *The New Crusade: Islamophobia and the Global War on Muslims*. California: University of California Press.
- Curiel, J. (2015). *Islam in America*. New York: Bloomsbury Publishing
- Esposito, J. L., & Kalin, I. (2011). *Islamophobia: The Challenge of Pluralism in the 21st Century*. New York: Oxford University Press.
- Foucault, M. (1977). *Discipline and Punish: the Birth of Prison*. New York: Vintage Books.
- Gjelten, T. (2015). *A Nation of Nations: A Great American Immigration Story*. New York: Simon & Schuster.
- Guindi, Y. E. (2019). *The Selected Works of Yussef El Guindi*. New York: Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Havis, A. (2010). *American Political Plays after 9/11*. Illinois: Southern Illinois University Press.
- Hilal, M. (2021). *Innocent until Proven Muslim: Islamophobia, the War on Terror, and the Muslim Experiences since 9/11*. Minneapolis: Broadleaf Books.
- Ithawi, H. N. H. (2018). *Arab-American Playwrights: Hyphenated Identities and Cultural In-Betweenness*. [Doctoral dissertation, the University of Texas at Austin], <https://repositories.lib.utexas.edu>.
- Lacko, I. (2015). Freedom Stuck in the Throat: Yussef El Guindi's *Back of the Throat* through *Zlin Proceedings in Humanities*, 5, 257-265.
- Lean, N. C. (2012). *The Islamophobia Industry: How the Right Manufactures Hatred of Muslims*. London: Pluto Press.
- Lean, N.C. (2018). *Understanding Islam and the West: Critical Skills for Students*. New York: Rowman & Littlefield.
- Little, D. (2008). *American Orientalism: The United States and the Middle East since 1945*. Chapel Hill: The University of North Carolina Press.
- Love, E. (2017). *Islamophobia and Racism*. New York: New York University Press.
- Marr, T. (2006). *The Cultural Roots of American Islamicism*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
- Meer, N., & Noorani, T. (2008). A Sociological Comparison of anti-Semitism and anti-Muslim Sentiment in Britain. *The Sociological Review*, 56(2), 195-219.
- Mamdani, M. (2003). *Good Muslim, Bad Muslim: America, the Cold War and the Roots of Terror*. New York: Three Leaves Press Doubleday.
- Massad, J. A. (2007). *Desiring Arabs*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press
- Morey, P., Yaqin, A., & Forte, A. (2019). *Contesting Islamophobia: Anti-Muslim Prejudice in Media, Culture and Politics*. London: Bloomsbury Publishing
- Naber, N. (2012). *Arab America: Gender, Cultural Politics and Activism*. New York: New York University Press.
- Najib, k. (2022). *Spatialized Islamophobia*. New York: Routledge Taylor and Francis Group.
- Najjar, M. M. (2014). *Four Arab American Plays*. North Carolina: McFarland & Company, Inc., Publishers.
- Najjar, M. M. (2015). Threesome by Yussef El Guindi, Chris Coleman. *Theatre Journal*: 76 (3), 554-556.
- Patai, R. (1973). *The Arab Mind*. New York: Charles Scribner's Sons
- Said, E. W. (1978). *Orientalism*. London: Penguin Books.
- Said, E. W. (1983). *The World, the Text, and the Critic*. Cambridge, Massachusetts: Harvard University Press.
- Salaita, S. (2007). *Arab American Literary Fiction, Cultures and Politics*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Sardar, Z., & Davies, M.W. (2002). *Why Do People Hate America*. London: Cox & Wyman Ltd.

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Online ISSN: 3006-5895

Shaban, F. (1991). *Islam and Arabs in Early American Thought: The Roots of Orientalism in America*. North Carolina: The Acorn Press.

Shaheen, J. G. (2001). *Reel Bad Arabs: how Hollywood vilifies a People*. Massachusetts: Olive Branch Press.

Spellberg, D. A. (2013). *Thomas Jefferson's Qur'an: Islam and the Founders*. New York: Alfred A. Knopf.

Suleiman, M. W. (1999). *Arabs in America: Building a New Future*. Philadelphia: Temple University Press